

TRANSFORM

Just energy transition for all from the voices of Lombardy citizens

Report of the deliberative workshop conducted within the EU H2020 TRANSFORM project

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TRANSFORM

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Regione
Lombardia

FINLOMBARDA
FINANZIAMO SVILUPPO

Abstract

This report describes the process and the results of a deliberative workshop conducted online on 29 May 2021, in which 18 citizens residing in Lombardy expressed their opinions on how to implement a “Just Energy Transition for All”. Citizens gathered to learn, discuss, and deliver recommendations to Lombardy Region to render regional research and innovation actions for the energy transition more inclusive. The workshop is one of the components of a broader participatory process organized by the Giannino Bassetti Foundation along with Lombardy Region and Finlombarda. The workshop took place within the framework of the European project TRANSFORM, which aims to design and test pathways to involve citizens in regional research and innovation governance.

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Introduction

Every three years, Lombardy Region designs a strategic document aimed at defining regional research and innovation priorities (the Three-Year Strategic Program for Research, Innovation, and Technology Transfer). Citizens' needs have been at the basis of this strategy since its inception, but thanks to TRANSFORM – a European project coordinated by Giannino Bassetti Foundation - for the first time, regional needs have been identified directly from citizens.

In Spring 2021, around 1020 citizens have been engaged in a two stages participatory process, adopting a mix of quantitative and qualitative approaches (respectively a survey and deliberative workshop, which is described in this report). In the first citizen engagement stage, around 1,000 people living in Lombardy participated in a survey on regional needs and priorities for research and innovation. Based on results emerging from the survey, Giannino Bassetti Foundation, in dialogue with Lombardy Region and Finlombarda, decided to run a deliberative exercise to further discuss with a group of selected Lombardy residents one of the priorities raised by respondents in the survey: the energy transition. TRANSFORM partners in Lombardy decided to focus deliberative workshop on **“Just Energy Transition for All”** to ensure that the social dimension of the green transition was taken into account by Lombardy Region when building its strategic policies and ac-

tions in the field. During the workshop, participants developed recommendations that were delivered to Lombardy Region representatives and integrated in the Three-Years Strategic Program for Research, Innovation and Technological Transfer 2021-2023.

The model: the deliberative workshop

A deliberative workshop is one of the possible methodologies through which deliberative processes take place. In deliberative processes a group of citizens meets, informs, discusses and elaborates collective recommendations that are delivered to the decision-makers (politicians, public officials, etc.) who commissioned the deliberative process. For the citizens involved, taking part to deliberative processes is a great responsibility and opportunity to make their voices heard. For this reason, everyone must have the same chance of being selected, and the recruiting process should ideally be based on a random selection of citizens plus stratification based on key socio-demographic factors (e.g., age, gender, area of origin, etc.), in order to make up a microcosm (a mini-public) of the general public. Compared to other deliberative methodologies, the deliberative workshop is cheaper and faster (it can take place in one day). When complex issues are dis-

cussed (e.g., just energy transition as it is the case in TRANSFORM), through deliberative workshops citizens can provide a first analysis of the different elements revolving around a specific question, even if more time might be needed for more detailed considerations.

The deliberative workshop of the TRANSFORM project

In the TRANSFORM deliberative workshop participants met online (through a video-conferencing platform) for a full day on the 29th of May 2021, from 9.30 a.m. to 6 p.m. The discussion occurred in plenaries (18 participants) and breakout sessions (6 participants), supported

by professional facilitators. The workshop followed the standard format of deliberative dialogues:

- 1) An informative phase to present the objectives of the workshop, frame the deliberative process (in this case, the TRANSFORM project and the activities of the Lombardy cluster) and learn about the topic addressed, also thanks to the presence of experts with whom participants can interact.
- 2) A discussion phase to identify the key issues that need to be addressed (in this case, social justice questions related to the energy transition).
- 3) A final phase to formulate collective recommendations (in this case, addressed to Lombardy Region).

Figure 1 - Deliberative workshop with citizens in videoconference

The participants

The workshop was attended by 18 randomly selected citizens residing in Lombardy. The group was balanced by gender, province of residence, and age. The distribution of participants is illustrated below:

Gender/age	18-34	35-54	55 and over	Total
M	2	3	3	8
F	3	4	3	10
Total	5	7	6	18
LOMBARDY PROVINCE				
BERGAMO			2	
BRESCIA			2	
COMO			1	
CREMONA			1	
LECCO			1	
LODI			1	
MANTOVA			1	
MILANO			4	
MONZA E BRIANZA			1	
PAVIA			1	
SONDRIO			1	
VARESE			2	
Total			18	

Table 1 - Participant distribution

The designers, the commissioning public authority, and the funder

The workshop was organised by Fondazione Giannino Bassetti Foundation, Coordinator of the TRANSFORM project, along with the Lombardy Region and Finlombarda S.p.A., with the support of Simon Burall, Senior Advisor of Involve and expert in deliberative processes. The recruitment of participants (in accordance with the socio-demographic parameters indicated by TRANSFORM partners) was conducted by an agency specialized in social research (ALMAR Quality Research), which also contributed to facilitation. The recommendations obtained were delivered to the Directorate General Education, University, Research, Innovation, and Simplification of the Lombardy Region, which integrated them into the Three Years Strategic Plan for Research, Innovation, and Technology Transfer (2021-2023) with the support of Finlombarda. The European Commission financed the TRANSFORM project within the H2020 Framework Programme.

Issues (discussion phase)

In the discussion phase, citizens started their dialogue by identifying key actions for energy transition in Lombardy, which were grouped into the following macro-areas:

- Actions by citizens on the energy transition
- Information and communication
- Actions for mobility
- Better services and ecological incentives for public and private buildings
- Actions for drinking water
- Actions for waste disposal
- Green education in schools
- Training and innovation at work
- Digitisation of public administration
- Research.

Among the macro-areas described, participants identified three key priorities on which they have been focusing when elaborating the recommendations: **training and innovation at work, better services and green incentives for public and private buildings, and digitisation of public administration.**

Recommendations (deliberative phase)

For each macro-area, citizens analysed the related social justice issues and then unanimously drafted and approved a set of recommendations. Respectively in two cases and in one case, citizens stressed specific challenges (e.g., complex mechanisms to access incentives) and opportunities (e.g., creation of new green jobs) connected to the implementation of the recommendations.

Training and innovation at work

Recommendations

- Coordination/mapping of “flexible” companies
- Mapping of jobs at risk due to de-carbonisation actions
- Mapping the current and future needs (in terms of training and jobs)
- Better promotion of training courses for green jobs/skills
- Training for “green managers” for companies
- Training and collaboration between companies and universities for the development of new green jobs
- Courses for companies on green actions
- Internships on new green jobs (to acquire high quality skills, to access the labour market)
- Lifelong learning on energy transition
- Raising public awareness on energy transition
- Support to closed-loop agriculture (production, distribution/sales, vertical integration)
- Rewards/incentives/promotion to and for companies that make the transition well (depending on the size of the companies, incentives/rewards should be different), not only for those that start the process but also for those that continue to do so).

Challenge:

- Training/professional reconversion (challenging to change, not trivial)

Opportunities

- New jobs for people skilled on this topic
- Incentives for start-ups, new green companies
- Trainings starting in schools (courses, not just workshops - trainings also for teachers)

Better services and ecological incentives for public and private buildings

Recommendations

- Incentives to replace household appliances
- Mandatory standards for buildings with more than 10-12 apartments/households
- Electricity charging stations in residential buildings
- Ecological watchdogs (controlling energy waste in shops, etc.)
- Conversion of unused public buildings sold at low prices
- Going through companies or SMEs for incentives
- Easy procedures
- Support for reuse of reconditioned appliances or appliances from recycled material (even if partially)
- Recycling of remanufactured PCs for children and elderlies

Appendix - The programme of the day

The workshop was conducted based on the following agenda (with some minor changes in terms of timing during the event):

9.30 - 9.45

Greetings and a brief introduction to the project and the participatory process (plenary)

9.45 - 10.00

Introduction to the agenda, the “rules”, and issue of the day (plenary)

10.00 - 10.30

Breve presentazione di tutti – Ice breaker (plenaria)

10.30-10.50

Expert presentations (plenary)

10.50-11.10

Preparation of questions for the expert (break out rooms)

11.10-11.30

Questions to the expert (plenary)

11.30 - 12.00 BREAK

12.00-12.50

Energy transition in Lombardy: what is needed? (Break-out rooms)
What actions are needed to start an energy transition in Lombardy

Shared clustering in macro-categories together with the groups' participants

12.50-13.30

Plenary discussion and selection of 3 macro-categories (plenary)

13.30 - 14.30 LUNCH BREAK

14.30 - 15.15

Just Energy Transition for All in Lombardy (break-out rooms)
For each selected macro-category participants identify the social justice actions to be considered when implementing the actions for that macro-issue.

15.15 - 16.00

Discussion of the actions identified (plenary)

16.00 - 16.30 BREAK

16.30 - 17.15

Development of recommendations to be delivered to Lombardy Region for a Just Energy Transition for All in Lombardy (break-out rooms)

17.15 -17.45

Sharing breakout results and collective agreement on recommendations (plenary)

17.45 - 18.00

Feedback form and final comments (plenary)

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